

Loading-Path Dependent Time- and Frequency-Domain Multiaxial Variable Amplitude Fatigue Analysis for Marine Structural Reliability

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Abstract. Marine structures such as ships, offshore oil and gas platforms, offshore wind turbines, and marine energy facilities are constantly subjected to variable amplitude dynamic loads that lead to multiaxial fatigue damage and failure. Designing against fatigue failure and design for structural reliability are critically important aspects in marine structural design. In this paper, the path-dependent maximum range (PDMR), a time-domain loading-path dependent multiaxial variable amplitude cycle counting method and three associated moment-of-load path based multiaxial fatigue damage parameters developed over the last decade, is reviewed first. Then, the efforts in extending PDMR from the original time-domain analysis to frequency-domain analysis are summarized with the emphasis on the challenges encountered, solutions developed, and gaps remained. Subsequently, closed-form frequency-domain solutions of multiaxial fatigue damage are derived for the first time under the assumptions: (1) both normal and shear stress time histories are stationary, random, and Gaussian narrow-band, and (2) normal and shear stress time histories are correlated in both amplitude and phase angle. The average continuous relative phase is introduced to characterize the phase or nonlinearity effects, and the phase portraits method and the Herbert transform method are used to express the mathematical formulations. Finally, based on the deterministic frequency-domain solutions, probabilistic and reliability analysis is introduced into the frequency-domain PDMR, by which the uncertainties and variations in typical marine structure/material properties can be considered and evaluated.

Keywords: *Multiaxial fatigue, PDMR, cycle counting, time-domain, frequency-domain, durability and reliability, uncertainty quantification.*

1 Introduction

Cyclic wave, wind, tidal, current, and operational loads can lead to fatigue failure of marine structures, such as ships, offshore oil and gas platforms, offshore wind turbines, marine energy converters. These various loads result in multiaxial variable amplitude cyclic stresses at fatigue-prone locations, such as welds, in the marine structures [1]. Designing against fatigue failure, structural performance optimization, and design for structural reliability are particularly important for naval ships subjected to seaway loads, which are stochastic, dynamic, and constantly varying [2, 3]. To accurately predict fatigue damage/life and to ensure the safety and reliability of the designed marine structures, the following two aspects must be properly considered: (1) stress analysis methods that can relate a stress parameter to fatigue physics, and (2) fatigue life evaluation methods that can describe and interpret the observed complex fatigue phenomena. For the stress analysis part, the second author of this paper has developed traction structural stress method [4] and the associated master S-N curve approach [5] that can eliminate severe mesh-sensitivity as suffered by other methods and provide superior data correlation. The structural stress components in the welded structures can be derived from the nodal forces and nodal moments, which are usually the standard output of the common FEA software, such as Abaqus and Nastran. By further considering fatigue crack growth, loading, and plate thickness effects, the structural stress can be extended to more universal equivalent structural stress, which has demonstrated its capability in collapsing fatigue life data from various conditions into a single master S-N curve with a roughly linear mean curve in a log-log plot and a narrow scatter band [4, 5]. The structural stress method and the master S-N curve approach have been adopted by ASME Section VIII Division 2 code since 2007 as an alternative design approach and have been widely used in the industry since then. Healy [6-8] compared the traction structural stress method to other methods, such as hot-spot method, and has demonstrated its superiority in mesh-insensitivity and accuracy in fatigue analysis of offshore structures, such as FPSO in North Sea.

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To apply the traction structural stress method for complex structures and loading conditions, the authors of this paper have developed the Path-Dependent Maximum Range (PDMR), a loading-path dependent multiaxial variable amplitude cycle counting and fatigue damage/life assessment method [9, 10]. The basic concept of the PDMR method is to plot traction structural normal and shear stress time histories in an equivalent stress space, and then a maximum range criterion is recursively applied to break a given set of structural normal-shear stress time histories into cycles. The counted cycles can then be used to calculate fatigue damage with path-dependent multiaxial fatigue damage parameters. Advanced convex-hull algorithms for increasing PDMR efficiency [11] and the fundamental basis of PDMR in fracture mechanics [12] have been further developed. Compared with other methods, the PDMR method has two unique parts: (1) multiaxial cycle counting, which can be reduced to the well-known rainflow cycle counting method for uniaxial loading, and (2) loading-path related phase or nonproportionality effects, which can lead to different fatigue lives (depending on materials applied) between out-of-phase loading, e.g. 90 degree and in-phase, i.e. 0 degree in relative phase, for the same applied respective normal and shear stress amplitudes. With the same common PDMR cycle counting method, three loading-path dependent multiaxial fatigue damage parameters have been developed over the years: (1) first-order moment of load path [9, 10], (2) second-order moment of load path [13-16], and (3) second-moment of load path [17]. The framework of PDMR method is general enough to be applied to welded as well as non-welded structures, and it can also be applied to strain-based fatigue analysis [17]. With the original PDMR methods, the distance between any two data points is measured to determine a cycle and the values of the associated fatigue damage parameters in an equivalent stress space, essentially, a time-domain based analysis approach.

Frequency-domain fatigue analysis methods are becoming increasingly popular recently because of their unique advantages over the traditional time-domain methods [18]. However, when applying the PDMR fatigue damage parameters to frequency-domain multiaxial analysis, theoretical difficulties and practical challenges, such as how to develop transfer functions for nonlinear bending ratio and how to handle phase angle caused nonproportionality, become prominent. Healy [19] proposed a procedure to linearize the influence of bending ratio in narrow band traction structural stress applications and obtained both equivalent normal and in-plane shear structural stress transfer functions for a typical marine structure. Healy [20] further extended the traction structural stress method to cover wide banded applications and validated the results against the associated PDMR time-domain calculations. In these studies [19, 20], random phases were assigned to each frequency during the inverse Fourier Transform of both normal and in-plane shear structural stresses, consequently, there is no clear phase relation between the normal and shear stresses. However, both investigations indicated the importance of the in-plane shear in fatigue damage and multiaxial structural stress analysis became necessary [19, 20]. Based on Healy's work [19, 20], Ravi et al. [21, 22] proposed a frequency-domain PDMR method and demonstrated its efficiency as compared to the time-domain part. Pei et al. [23] further proposed a non-proportionality correlation function, which utilizes the power spectrum density (PSD) of normal and shear traction structural stresses and their cross-probability density function (CPSD), for fatigue analysis of nonproportional loadings. In [23], the correlation function is determined by comparing the time-domain PDMR results through a small-scale data-driven approach. A similar formula has been proposed by Pei et al. [24] with advanced data analysis through an artificial neural network approach. It should be noted that in all these analyses, correlation coefficient is used as the parameter for measuring non-proportionality or out-of-phase effects, which is controversial.

In this paper, the current state-of-the-art research on PDMR in both time-domain and frequency domain are reviewed. A new average continuous relative phase is then introduced to characterize the phase or nonlinearity effects with phase portraits method and the Hilbert transform method. With the new nonproportionality factor, closed-form solutions of multiaxial fatigue damage are derived under the following two assumptions about both normal and shear stress time histories: (1) stationary, random, and Gaussian narrow-band, and (2) normal and shear stress time histories are correlated in both amplitude and phase. Subsequently, the distinctive features of the new nonproportionality factor, the new frequency-domain PDMR fatigue analysis method, and their advantages over other existing methods are demonstrated through several examples. Finally, probabilistic and reliability analysis is introduced into the frequency-domain PDMR method to demonstrate its potential in quantifying the uncertainties and variations of typical marine structures.

2 PDMR multiaxial cycle counting and damage parameters

2.1 PDMR cycle counting method

Traction structural stress for welded structures is formulated by representing the stress state on a hypothetical crack plane in the form of membrane and bending stress components. Consider the stress state at a weld toe location along a through thickness hypothetical cut in Fig.1 (a), the three stress components exposed by the cut are σ_x , τ_y

and τ_z . Transverse shear τ_z is usually negligible in most applications. Then, the loading path can be drawn in an equivalent normal-shear stress plane, and eventually PDMR cycle counting and damage and life assessment can be conducted as shown in Fig.1(b).

Figure 1 (a) Traction multiaxial structural stresses along weld toe on a hypothetical cut surface (local x' - z' plane), and (b) The PDMR cycle counting procedure for identifying half-cycles with a turning point (R), projected turning point (R^*), and virtual path (RR^*) definition.

The main aim of PDMR cycle counting is to sequentially find the maximum stress range in the equivalent stress space until all paths are counted and counted only once. The general procedures for PDMR are as follows [9, 10], Fig.1(b):

1. Map normal and shear stress histories to $\sigma - \sqrt{\beta}\tau$ plane, where β is the equivalency factor between the normal and shear components in the stress plane.
2. Search for the maximum stress range for a given set of data.
3. Identify monotonically increasing load path segments from the starting point and find all turning points, e.g. R , Fig.1(b). Use a virtual circular path to determine the corresponding projected turning point, R^* , Fig.1 (b). The loading path ORR^*T is used to calculate the equivalent stress range for this half cycle. The virtual path length RR^* is associated with a negative cycle, and its contribution to damage can be considered for consistency purposes but neglecting negative cycles will not make significant differences [12].
4. Repeat step-1 to step-3 for all the segments that have not been counted. The collected half-cycles (both positive and negative) and the corresponding multiaxial fatigue damage parameters are used to estimate fatigue damage with the damage accumulation rule (Miner's rule).

It should be noted that the PDMR cycle counting method can lead to the same results as obtained from the rainflow cycle counting method for uniaxial loading. Additionally, because of the common maximum range measure, the PDMR cycle counting method can be easily extended to 3-D stress space, where a normal stress and two shear stress components (e.g., in-plane shear and through thickness shear) are operative. By contrast, the concepts of peaks and valleys in the rainflow cycle counting method cannot be extended to 2-D or 3-D stress space, indicating the limitations of the rainflow concept.

2.2 PDMR multiaxial fatigue damage parameters

Mathematically, the three loading-path dependent PDMR multiaxial fatigue damage parameters can be described in Fig.2 [11-14].

Figure 2 PDMR multiaxial fatigue damage parameters in terms of geometrical interpretation

2.2.1 Zeroth moment of load path (ZMLP)

PDMR ZMLP, a path length-based equivalent fatigue damage parameter, is defined in Eq. (1) [9, 10].

$$\Delta S_e = \int d\sigma_e = \int \sqrt{(d\sigma)^2 + \beta(d\tau)^2} \quad (1)$$

The circumferential length of an ellipse is

$$C = 4A \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta = 4AE(e) \quad (2)$$

where $e = \sqrt{1 - B^2/A^2}$ is the eccentricity, A and B are respectively the lengths of the semi-major and semi-minor axes, and the function $E(e)$, Eq. (3), is the complete elliptic integral of the second kind.

$$E(e) = \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (3)$$

Eq. (3) is not an elementary function and therefore there is no simple analytical solution. However, the integral in Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) can be evaluated using numerical approaches or approximate analytical formulae.

2.2.2 First moment of load path (FMLP)

PDMR FMLP multiaxial fatigue damage parameter can be expressed in Eq. (4) [13-16].

$$\Delta S_e = (\Delta\sigma_e)(1 + \alpha g_{NP}) \quad (4)$$

$$g_{NP} = \frac{\int_{\overline{AB}} r' |\sin(\theta)| ds'}{\int_{\overline{AB}} R |\sin(\theta)| ds'} = \frac{\int_{\overline{AB}} r' |\sin(\theta)| ds'}{2R^2} \quad (5)$$

α in Eq. (4) is a material sensitivity parameter. It is found that $\alpha \approx 1$ gives a reasonable correlation for various structural steels and α varies from 0.35 to 0.5 for aluminum alloys, depending on the ductility of aluminum alloys examined [13-16]. g_{NP} in Eq. (5) represents the nonproportionality of a loading path in terms of the ratio between the integral of an actual loading path and the integral of the circle, which is “most nonproportional”, Fig.2.

2.2.3 Second moment of load path (SMLP)

If $x = \sigma$, $y = \sqrt{\beta}\tau$, and $dl = \sqrt{(d\sigma)^2 + \beta(d\tau)^2}$, PDMR SMLP for a full cycle with a general loading path can be expressed in Eq. (6)-Eq. (9) [17].

$$\Delta S_e = \sqrt[3]{6I_E} \quad (6)$$

$$I_E = \sqrt{I_X^2 + I_Y^2} = \sqrt{I_x^2 + I_y^2 + 2I_{xy}^2} \quad (7)$$

$$I_x = \frac{I_x + I_y}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{I_x - I_y}{2}\right)^2 + I_{xy}^2} \quad (8)$$

$$I_y = \frac{I_x + I_y}{2} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{I_x - I_y}{2}\right)^2 + I_{xy}^2} \quad (9)$$

In the local coordinate system $x - y$, the second moment of load path with respect to x - and y - axes and xy (product) are expressed in Eq. (10)

$$I_x = \int y^2 dl \quad I_y = \int x^2 dl \quad I_{xy} = \int xy dl \quad (10)$$

In the principal coordinate $X - Y$, the corresponding moments are shown in Eq. (11)

$$I_X = \int Y^2 dl \quad I_Y = \int X^2 dl \quad I_{XY} = \int XY dl = 0 \quad (11)$$

Eq. (7) indicates that I_E is a rotational invariant because of constant I_X and I_Y for a given loading path.

2.3 PDMR damage and life evaluation without using cycle counting

A fatigue S-N curve can often be expressed as $(\Delta\sigma)^k N = C$, with the exponent k close to 3. N is cycle to failure and C is a constant. In fact, in most of the engineering design standards, such as British Standards [25] and DNV standard [26] the recommended k value is exactly 3. For a constant $k = 3$, with the definition of second moment of load path, I , Eq. (10), Eq. (11), and Eq.(6), the fatigue S-N curve can be written as $IN = C$ or $I_E = \frac{(\Delta S_e)^3}{6}$ for a full cycle, which is the simplest form of damage-cycle relationship. The most important physical implication of the reciprocal relationship between I and N is that I itself is linear damage, which is additive. Therefore, total damage can be obtained by simply adding loading paths in an accumulative manner, and a cycle counting procedure is not required any more. It is also demonstrated recently that [27], for uniaxial variable amplitude loading, the fatigue damages calculated with the accumulated second moment are similar to the results obtained from rainflow cycle counting for narrow-band data. For broad-band data the differences are large, and additional factors need to be considered [27].

3 Frequency-domain PDMR

Several existing nonproportionality measures are briefly discussed first, and then a new potential non-proportionality factor using continuous relative phase is introduced. The equations of the new non-proportionality measure for three PDMR fatigue damage parameters are derived for later frequency-domain PDMR analysis.

3.1 Common nonproportionality measures of loading paths

To characterize nonproportionality of loading paths, Pei et al. [23, 24] proposed a correlation function $\Psi(\rho)$ for PDMR based frequency-domain fatigue evaluation of nonproportional loading paths. $\Psi(\rho)$ is an empirical 8th order polynomial function of correlation coefficient ρ ($-1 \leq \rho \leq 1$), which is used to correct equivalent traction stress PSD obtained from the proportional loading. It was hoped that $\rho = \pm 1$ represents proportional loading and $\rho = 0$ represents the highest non-proportionality of loading path (90 deg out-of-phase for an ellipse). Time-domain PDMR generated data with a range of non-proportionality values provided the best fit to the model [22, 23]. However, it should be noted that the fit curve shows a large data scatter band in $\Psi(\rho)$, especially for the data around $\rho = 0$, that can lead to significant variations in the predicted fatigue damage. Further investigations showed that the correlation coefficient ρ may be not a proper parameter to measure loading path nonproportionality and this can be clearly demonstrated from the examples shown in Fig.3 [17].

Fig.3(a) shows a circle and several ellipses with different aspect ratios, which are defined as B/A , which is the ratio between minor axis B and major axis A of an ellipse. A reasonable non-proportionality parameter must give different values for these different loading paths, however, the values of data correlation coefficient ρ for all these loading paths are 0.0, clearly indicating that the correlation coefficient ρ is not an appropriate parameter for measuring the out-of-phase or nonproportional effects. Fig.3(b) illustrates several ellipses with the same aspect ratio ($B/A = 1/3$), but with different orientation angles. With a reasonable out-of-phase or non-proportionality parameter, these ellipses should give the same values of non-proportionality, however, the correlation coefficient ρ values for all these ellipses with the same aspect ratio are very different, ranging from 0 to about 0.8, further demonstrating that correlation coefficient ρ is not a proper parameter for measuring the out-of-phase or the non-proportionality effects.

Figure 3 (a) Correlation coefficient $\rho = 0$ for ellipses with different aspect ratios, and (b) the ellipses with the same aspect ratio $B/A = 1/3$ but with different correlation coefficient ρ values due to different orientation angles

Bolchoun et al. [28, 29] set up conditions for a qualified non-proportionality parameter f_{NP} :

(1) in the range of $0 \leq f_{NP} \leq 1$, with $f_{NP} = 0$ representing proportional and $f_{NP} = 1$ the “most non-proportional” case

(2) f_{NP} must be independent of the coordinate system

(3) must be applicable to any arbitrary time-dependent loading paths

In fact, recognizing the coordinate dependency of ρ , Bolchoun et al. [28, 29] introduced a non-proportionality parameter, Eq. (12), which is based on ρ but it has an integral structure and hence satisfying all above three conditions. θ In Eq. (12) represents the rotation angle of a critical plane.

$$f_{NP} = 1 - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} \rho^2 d\theta \quad (0 \leq f_{NP} \leq 1) \quad (12)$$

Several other different non-proportionality parameters have been proposed. For example, Chu et al. [30], Bishop [31], Gaier et al. [32, 33], Riess et al. [34] introduced various ratios of moments of inertia I as non-proportionality parameters, and an example is shown in Eq. (13) [34].

$$f_{NP} = \sqrt{\frac{I_2}{I_1}} \quad (0 \leq f_{NP} \leq 1) \quad (13)$$

Larsen [35] proposed to use principal component analysis (PCA) for quantifying non-proportionality for the first time. PCA has been extensively used in statistical analysis, and it is based on reducing the number of signals to their principal components.

3.2 Continuous relative phase as a nonproportionality parameter

For a sinusoidal time-history $x(t)$, Eq. (14), and its time derivative, $\dot{x}(t)$, Eq. (15), the instantaneous phase angle θ can be expressed in Eq. (16).

$$x(t) = A \cos(\theta) \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{x}(t) = -A \sin(\theta) \quad (15)$$

$$\tan(\theta) = \frac{\dot{x}(t)}{x(t)} \text{ or } \theta = \arctan \left[\frac{\dot{x}(t)}{x(t)} \right] \quad (16)$$

In analogy, for any two arbitrary continuous varying time functions $x_1(t)$ and $x_2(t)$, the phase angles of the two signals θ_1 , θ_2 , and the approximate instantaneous phase angle difference δ between these two signals are respectively shown in Eq. (17), Eq.(18), and Eq.(19).

$$\theta_1 = \arctan \left[\frac{\dot{x}_1(t)}{x_1(t)} \right] \quad (17)$$

$$\theta_2 = \arctan \left[\frac{\dot{x}_2(t)}{x_2(t)} \right] \quad (18)$$

$$\delta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 = \arctan \left[\frac{\dot{x}_1(t)x_2(t) - \dot{x}_2(t)x_1(t)}{x_1(t)x_2(t) + \dot{x}_1(t)\dot{x}_2(t)} \right] \quad (19)$$

The instantaneous relative phase can be more accurately and consistently obtained from the Hilbert transform [36], Eq. (20).

$$\delta = \theta_1 - \theta_2 = \arctan \left[\frac{H_1(t)x_2(t) - H_2(t)x_1(t)}{x_1(t)x_2(t) + H_1(t)H_2(t)} \right] \quad (20)$$

The average relative phase $\bar{\delta}$ over a certain period T can be defined in Eq. (21).

$$\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \delta(t) dt \quad (21)$$

Healy [20] argued that, for some marine structures, even for wide-banded response spectra, the normal structural stress (NSS) and shear structural stress (TSS) corresponding to each component of equal frequency in the IFT should be largely in-phase. In other words, whatever physical phenomena that causes a given frequency contribution would generate stresses that were primarily in phase. This represents the least conservative strategy in terms of fatigue damage, and the same random phase was assigned to both normal and shear stresses components. However, in many applications, especially in multi-input multi-output system (MIMO) [37] phase difference and loading amplitude ratio are often correlated. The average relative phase in Eq. (21) provides an effective way to simplify the fatigue analysis for these special applications.

3.3 PDMR damage parameters as functions of phase difference δ

Since nonproportional or out-of-phase loading paths could be more damaging than proportional or in-phase loading paths, it is critically important to build the relationship between a proposed nonproportionality parameter and the selected fatigue damage parameter. Instead of using correlation coefficient ρ , ρ related parameters, ratios in moments of inertia, and PCA, this paper directly links the three PDMR fatigue damage parameters to the average relative phase angle, which was originally linked to sinusoidal loadings but can be approximately and effectively applied to other general loading conditions. For the applied normal and shear stresses expressed in Eq. (22), the resulting loading path is an ellipse with the major axis A , Eq. (23), and minor axis B , Eq. (24). When $\delta = 0$, the loading path is in-phase or proportional and the length of a quarter of the straight load path can be expressed in Eq. (25) [9].

$$\sigma = \sigma_0 \sin(\theta) \quad \tau = \tau_0 \sin(\theta - \delta) \quad (22)$$

$$A = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2) - \sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}}} \quad (23)$$

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2) + \sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}}} \quad (24)$$

$$C_P = \sqrt{\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2} \quad (25)$$

3.3.1 $\Phi_0(\delta)$ for zeroth moment of load path (path length)

A quarter of the circumference of an ellipse can be calculated from the complete elliptic integral of the second kind, Eq. (26). The eccentricity e as a function of phase difference δ is expressed in Eq. (27). The nonproportionality function $\Phi_0(\delta)$ can be expressed as Eq. (28).

$$C_{NP} = A \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (26)$$

$$e = \sqrt{1 - B^2/A^2} = \sqrt{\frac{2\sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}}{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2) + \sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta\tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta\sigma_0^2\tau_0^2\sin^2(\delta)}}} \quad (27)$$

$$\Phi_0(\delta) = \frac{C_{NP}}{C_P} = \frac{A}{C_P} \int_0^{\pi/2} \sqrt{1 - e^2 \sin^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (28)$$

When $A = B$, $\Phi_0(\delta) = \frac{\pi A}{2C_P} \approx 1.114$.

3.3.2 $\Phi_1(\delta)$ for first moment of load path

The damage D_{NP} and the nonproportionality factor g_{NP} previously defined for first moment of load path [13-16] are respectively given in Eq. (29) and Eq. (30), for a quarter of an ellipse. The nonproportionality function $\Phi_1(\delta)$ can be expressed as Eq. (31), where the aspect ratio of the ellipse η is expressed in Eq. (32).

$$D_{NP} = \int_0^{\pi/2} r \sin \theta dl = \int_0^{\pi/2} y' dl = \int_0^{\pi/2} B \sin \theta \sqrt{A^2 \sin^2 \theta + B^2 \cos^2 \theta} d\theta = \frac{AB}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 - e^2} + \frac{\arcsin(e)}{e} \right) \quad (29)$$

$$g_{NP} = \frac{D_{NP}}{D_{Max}} = \frac{AB}{2R^2} \left(\sqrt{1 - e^2} + \frac{\arcsin(e)}{e} \right) \quad (30)$$

$$\Phi_1(\delta) = \frac{C_{NP}}{C_P} = \frac{A(1 + \alpha g_{NP})}{C_P} = \frac{A}{C_P} \left\{ 1 + \alpha \frac{\eta}{2} \left[\eta + \frac{\arcsin(\sqrt{1 - \eta^2})}{\sqrt{1 - \eta^2}} \right] \right\} \quad (31)$$

$$\eta = \frac{B}{A} = \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta \tau_0^2) - \sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta \tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta \sigma_0^2 \tau_0^2 \sin^2(\delta)}}{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta \tau_0^2) + \sqrt{(\sigma_0^2 + \beta \tau_0^2)^2 - 4\beta \sigma_0^2 \tau_0^2 \sin^2(\delta)}}} \quad (32)$$

When $A = B$, $\Phi_1(\delta) = \frac{1+\alpha}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\Phi_1(\delta) = \frac{1+\alpha}{\sqrt{2}} = 1.414$ for α .

3.3.3 $\Phi_2(\delta)$ for second moment of load path

The principal moments of inertia I_X and I_Y for a quarter of an ellipse can be calculated respectively from Eq. (33) and Eq. (34). With the definition of effective second moment of inertia, Eq. (35), the effective stress range, Eq. (36), the nonproportionality function $\Phi_2(\delta)$ can be expressed as Eq. (37) [17].

$$I_X = \int_0^{\pi/2} Y^2 dl = \int_0^{\pi/2} B^2 \sin^2 \theta \sqrt{A^2 \sin^2 \theta + B^2 \cos^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (33)$$

$$I_Y = \int_0^{\pi/2} X^2 dl = \int_0^{\pi/2} A^2 \cos^2 \theta \sqrt{A^2 \sin^2 \theta + B^2 \cos^2 \theta} d\theta \quad (34)$$

$$I_E = \sqrt{I_X^2 + I_Y^2} \quad (35)$$

$$C_{NP} = \sqrt[3]{3I_E} \quad (36)$$

$$\Phi_2(\delta) = \frac{C_{NP}}{C_P} = \frac{\sqrt[3]{3I_E}}{C_P} \quad (37)$$

When $A = B$, $\Phi_2(\delta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt[3]{\frac{3\sqrt{2}}{4}} \approx 1.056$.

3.4 Narrow-Band PDMR multiaxial damage estimation

3.4.1 Uniaxial loading

In contrast to examining time sequence in time-domain analysis, fatigue damage in frequency-domain is estimated with the frequency contents only, i.e. spectral power density (PSD) and the associated moments with various orders. All phase information and time-sequence effects are lost in frequency-domain analysis. This approach is acceptable for scenarios under certain assumptions. For uniaxial narrow-band data, the common assumptions for obtaining exact solutions are the data is stationary, Gaussian and random [38-40]. A random process is one where the future movements of the process cannot be represented by any mathematical expression with certainty at any time. A stationary process is one where the statistical properties measured at a particular time are identical with the statistics measured across the ensemble at any other time. A Gaussian random process is a

process where the random variable follows the normal distribution. The probability density distribution of a zero mean random variable with Gaussian distribution is listed in Eq. (38).

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma_x \sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x}{\sigma_x}\right)^2} \quad (38)$$

The power spectral density (PSD) or autospectral density function of a signal gives an indication of the average power contained frequencies, and it can be expressed in the units of signal squared over radian or Hertz. PSD can be expressed the form of two-sided PSD $S_{xx}(f)$ or more commonly used one-sided PSD $G_{xx}(f) = 2S_{xx}(f)$. Where $f = 2\pi/\omega$, f is regular frequency in Hertz and ω is circular frequency in radian. Specifically, the mean value μ_x and variance σ_x^2 of $x(t)$ can be expressed in Eq. (39) and Eq. (40), respectively.

$$\mu_x = E[x(t)] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} xp(x)dx \quad (39)$$

$$R_{xx}(0) = E[x(t)x(t)] = \sigma_x^2 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x^2 p(x)dx = \int_0^{+\infty} G_{xx}(f)df \quad (40)$$

The n-th moment of PSD function $G_{xx}(f)$ can be defined in Eq. (41)

$$m_n = \int_0^{+\infty} f^n G(f)df \quad (41)$$

Based on Rice's work [38], Bendat [39, 40] formulated the frequency-domain solutions for the fatigue damage of structures subject to random loading. Important results include:

The number of zero crossing per unit time, Eq. (42).

$$E[0] = \sqrt{\frac{m_2}{m_0}} \quad (42)$$

The number of peaks per unit time, Eq. (43).

$$E[P] = \sqrt{\frac{m_4}{m_2}} \quad (43)$$

Irregularity factor, Eq. (44).

$$\gamma = \frac{E[0]}{E[P]} \quad (44)$$

The irregularity factor γ varies between 0 and 1. For narrow-band signal, γ approaches 1, and for wide-band or broad-band signal, γ values move to the side of 0. With the narrow-band assumption, the positive valleys or troughs and negative peaks are ignored. Additionally, all positive peaks are matched with the corresponding troughs or valleys of similar magnitude regardless of whether they form stress cycles.

The relationship between the applied load/stress amplitude or range and the cycles to failure for high-cycle failure can be mathematically described by the fatigue S-N curve, shown in Eq. (45)

$$S^k N = C \text{ or } N = CS^{-k} \text{ or } S = \left(\frac{C}{N}\right)^{\frac{1}{k}} \quad (45)$$

Materials constants C and k in Eq. (45) can be statistically obtained from constant-amplitude loading tests with several load levels. For variable amplitude loading, cycle counting needs to be used to convert the variable amplitude loading into a set of cycles with equivalent constant amplitude or range. For a given cycle i and the corresponding stress range S_i , the linear fatigue damage caused in i cycle is $D_i = \frac{1}{N_i} = \frac{S_i^k}{C}$. Assume that the PDF of

the stress range is $p(S)$, the expected fatigue damage $E[D]$ for a given time duration T with the number of peaks per unit time $E[P]$ then can be expressed in an integral form, Eq. (46).

$$E[D] = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{N(S_i)} = E[P] \frac{T}{C} \int_0^{+\infty} S^k p(S) dS \quad (46)$$

Eq. (46) can be solved in a closed form if one knows the analytical expressions of $p(S)$, which can be obtained from counting cycles in the time-domain approach or from analyzing the moments of PSD in the frequency-domain for a given block of representative loading history. Bendat [39, 40] presented the theoretical basis for the first frequency domain fatigue model, the so called narrow-band solution. For narrow-band processes, peaks and valleys are placed symmetrically around the mean value and the stress amplitude distribution coincides with the distribution of a local peak, which follows Rayleigh distribution. Additionally, the number of peaks is equal to the number of cycles in a counting method. For narrow-band processes, $E[P] = E[0]$, resulting in Eq. (47) [39-42].

$$E[D(T)]_{NB} = E[0] \frac{T}{C} \int_0^{+\infty} S^k \frac{S}{4m_0} e^{-\frac{S^2}{8m_0}} dS = E[0] \frac{T}{C} (\sqrt{2m_0})^k \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{k}{2}\right) \quad (47)$$

Where T is the time duration over which the fatigue damage will be calculated and $\Gamma(\)$ is the gamma function. Eq. (47) is exact for a strictly defined narrow-band process and fatigue damage is determined solely in terms of the spectral moments up to m_4 . The narrow band solution in Eq. (47) is obtained by substituting the Rayleigh pdf of peaks or stress ranges and noting that the total number of cycles in time T is $E[0] \times T$. When a signal is wide-band, the narrow-band solutions overestimate the probability of large stress ranges, and any damage calculated will therefore be overconservative. In practice for many structures the response is neither narrow band nor wide band but somewhere in between. Designers have tended to lean towards a narrow band approach, and such approaches have been practiced by Miles [40], Williams and Rinne [41], and Hallam [42] for simpler and conservative results as compared with more complex wide-band solutions.

Miner's linear damage summation rule for fatigue failure is defined in Eq. (48):

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{n_i}{N_i} = 1 \quad (48)$$

3.4.2 Multiaxial loading

In this paper we use proportional stress range as the basis and consider non-proportional or out-of-phase effects as corrected solutions by considering the average continuous relative phase δ for the three PDMR multiaxial fatigue damage parameters through nonproportionality function $\Phi(\delta)$. Consider a pair of stationary, random, and Gaussian stress process $\{s_\sigma(t), s_\tau(t)\}$ with respective zero means and normal distributions. Fatigue damage $D(T)$ can be estimated with the help of $G_{\sigma\sigma}(f)$, $G_{\tau\tau}(f)$, and $\Phi(\delta)$

In time-domain multiaxial random fatigue problems, for any given positive or negative normal stress $s_\sigma(t)$ and shear stress $s_\tau(t)$ in a time t , the corresponding constructed in-phase or proportional stress $s_p(t)$ can be expressed in Eq. (49).

$$s_p(t)^2 = s_\sigma(t)^2 + \beta s_\tau(t)^2 \quad (49)$$

For a given set of continuous normal and shear stress data histories, the autocorrection functions of the stress components can be expressed in Eq. (50)-Eq. (52),

$$R_{\sigma\sigma}(0) = E[s_\sigma(t)^2] = \int_0^{+\infty} G_{\sigma\sigma}(f) df \quad (50)$$

$$R_{\tau\tau}(0) = E[s_\tau(t)^2] = \int_0^{+\infty} G_{\tau\tau}(f) df \quad (51)$$

$$R_P(0) = E[s_P(t)^2] = \int_0^{+\infty} G_P(f)df \quad (52)$$

Combining Eq. (49) and Eq. (52), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{+\infty} G_P(f)df &= \int_0^{+\infty} G_{\sigma\sigma}(f)df + \beta \int_0^{+\infty} G_{\tau\tau}(f)df \\ &= \int_0^{+\infty} [G_{\sigma\sigma}(f) + \beta G_{\tau\tau}(f)]df \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

Or

$$G_P(f) = G_{\sigma\sigma}(f) + \beta G_{\tau\tau}(f) \quad (54)$$

The non-proportional equivalent structural stress PSD can be expressed in Eq. (55).

$$G_{NP}(f) = \Phi(\delta)G_P(f) \quad (55)$$

Therefore, the zeroth-moment of the narrow-band proportional loadings is obtained, Eq. (56)

$$\begin{aligned} m_0 &= \int_0^{+\infty} G_{NP}(f)df = \Phi(\delta) \int_0^{+\infty} G_P(f)df = \Phi(\delta) \int_0^{+\infty} [G_{\sigma\sigma}(f) + \beta G_{\tau\tau}(f)]df \\ &= \Phi(\delta) \left[\int_0^{+\infty} G_{\sigma\sigma}(f)df + \beta \int_0^{+\infty} G_{\tau\tau}(f)df \right] = \Phi(\delta)(m_{\sigma 0} + \beta m_{\tau 0}) \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

Fatigue damage can be estimated by combining Eq. (56) and Eq. (47). The safety or failure status can be updated by comparing the fatigue damage estimated with the failure criterion, Eq. (48).

4 Results and discussion

Three types of examples are provided to demonstrate the new concepts and procedures introduced in this paper: (1) how to calculate the average continuous relative phase or average phase difference, (2) fatigue estimations for narrow-band analysis, (3) reliability analysis based on the formula.

4.1 Average continuous relative phase

1. Two sinusoidal signals with the same frequency but with a phase shift

Fig.4(a) illustrates sinusoidal function $x_1(t) = \sin(2t)$ and $x_2(t) = \sin\left(2t - \frac{\pi}{6}\right)$ with $t \in [0, 2\pi]$ and Fig.4(b) shows the continuous relative phase $\delta(t)$ calculated from Eq. (19) using the phase portraits method. In this example, the two functions and their derivatives are normalized $[-1, 1]$ to reduce oscillations [36]. It is expected that the phase difference is constant, which is $-\frac{\pi}{6} = -0.524$ in radian or 30° in deg. Clearly, the average continuous relative phase angle $\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \delta(t)dt = -\frac{\pi}{6}$.

Figure 4 The continuous relative phase of two sinusoidal functions with a known phase shift

2. The continuous relative phase of two asynchronous functions with known frequency ratios

Fig.5 (a) illustrates asynchronous sinusoidal function $x_1(t) = \sin(2t)$ and $x_2(t) = \sin(5t)$ with $t \in [0, 2\pi]$ and Fig.5(b) shows the continuous relative phase $\delta(t)$ calculated from Eq. (19) using the phase portraits method. Again, these two functions and their derivatives are normalized $[-1, 1]$ to reduce oscillations [36]. It is found from Fig.5(b) that the phase difference of the two functions moves linearly from in-phase to out-of-phase and then get back to in-phase and repeat the process as time goes on. The average continuous relative phase angle for this set of data is $\bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \delta(t) dt = 0$ indicating the two functions have no constant or stable correlation in terms of phase angle. Asynchronous multiaxial loadings have been studied experimentally and analytically for a long time, for example [47], but the phase difference has been unclear and intriguing or arbitrary multiaxial loading until now. Eq. (19) and Eq. (20) provide quantitative parameters for measuring the phase difference and open new potential opportunities to effectively characterize multiaxial fatigue data. It should be noted that both the phase portraits method and the Hilbert transform method generate similar relative phase results for the asynchronous functions [36].

Figure 5 The continuous relative phase of two asynchronous functions with known frequency ratios

4.2 Nonproportional narrow-band multiaxial fatigue damage estimation

The first moment of load path PDMR multiaxial fatigue damage parameter is used here to demonstrate the concepts introduced in this paper. Fig.6 shows the relationship between the nonproportionality factor $\Phi_1(\delta)$ as a function of phase difference δ at different values of stress ratio τ_0/σ_0 . Material factor $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 3$ are assumed in plotting Fig.6. It is found that nonproportionality factor $\Phi_1(\delta)$ increases with phase difference first, once reaches a peak then decreases at about $\delta = \pi/2$. Similarly, $\Phi_1(\delta)$ increases with τ_0/σ_0 before decreases after reaching a peak. These observations are consistent with the intuitions. Combining Eq. (47) and Eq. (56), we have the

$E[D(T)]_{NB} = E[0] \frac{T}{C} (\sqrt{2\Phi_1(\delta)} (m_{\sigma_0} + \beta m_{\tau_0}))^k \Gamma(1 + \frac{k}{2})$. The damage ratio between nonproportional loading and proportional loading can be expressed as $D_{NP}/D_P = (\sqrt{\Phi_1(\delta)})^k$. Fig.6 shows the damage ratio D_{NP}/D_P as a function of phase difference at different levels of stress ratio τ_0/σ_0 . $k = 3$ is used here.

Figure 6 (a) Nonproportionality function $\Phi_1(\delta)$ as a function of phase difference δ , and (b) fatigue damage ratio D_{NP}/D_P as a function of relative phase difference δ .

4.3 Uncertainty quantification and reliability analysis

Uncertainty and reliability analysis is important in the design of marine structures [48]. Uncertainties are associated with almost every step of determining fatigue loads and load effects, complicating fatigue reliability assessments, for example, uncertainties of applied load, material properties, and fatigue models [49]. The time-domain and frequency domain methods developed in this paper are all deterministic, in terms of loading-related parameters, the corresponding probabilistic analysis methods need to be developed for the PDMR to account for loading uncertainties. It should be noted that complete reliability analysis requires load-strength interaction, with which the uncertainties in resistance from materials and structures also need to be considered. Based on comprehensive data review and extensive data collection and analysis, Dong [5] developed a master S-N curve, which tabulated the values of several probabilistic distribution parameters, such as the intercepts and slopes of the S-N curves at typical failure probability levels in terms of standard deviation (std). Based on the master S-N curve, fatigue life or damage calculated from Eq. (47) at typical reliability levels can be assessed. The conversion of the values from the master S-N curve to the values of the S-N curve used in this paper is shown in Table 1. Extending the current deterministic time-domain and frequency-domain PDMR by incorporating probabilistic and uncertainty analysis for the reliability analysis of marine structures is one of several planned research directions for PDMR technologies.

Table 1 Values of traction structural stress master S-N curve parameters [5]

Master S-N Curve	Statistics	C_s	h	Master S-N Curve	$C=(C_s)^k$	$k = -1/h$
$\Delta S_s = C_s N^h$	+3 std	31796.1	-0.32	$S^k N = C$	1.175×10^{14}	3.125
	+2 std	28626.5			8.46×10^{13}	
	mean	19930.2			2.72×10^{13}	
	-2 std	13578.8			8.22×10^{12}	
	-3 std	12492.6			6.33×10^{12}	

It should be noted that the phase angle studied in this paper is treated as constant, in a statistical sense. However, in practice, phase angle might be constant for a given loading/weather condition but might be more like a variable over the life of marine structure because of variable operations and loading from different angles and directions. A common way to tackle this issue is to separate a loading history into different segments, each has a characteristic phase angle corresponding to a specific loading condition. If a characteristic phase angle does not exist for a given load case, the assumptions under which this method is developed are violated and nonstationary approaches should be considered.

5 Conclusions

The time-domain PDMR multiaxial cycle counting and the associated three fatigue damage parameters are briefly reviewed in this paper. The corresponding frequency-domain PDMR and the associated developments, challenges, and potential issues, especially the nonproportionality parameters, are also described. An average continuous relative phase is introduced in this paper as a new nonproportionality parameter for accounting out-of-phase and nonproportional effects of loading paths. The mathematical relationships between the relative phase or phase difference and the three PDMR fatigue damage parameters are established in a closed form. For multiaxial fatigue loading with uniaxial narrow-band stationary, random, and Gaussian process in both normal and shear stress time histories, simple closed-form solutions are derived based on the available solutions for uniaxial loading and the nonproportional function. These narrow-band solutions can be best used for the scenarios, where normal and shear stress components are correlated in both amplitude and phase. The solutions can also be used for wide-band applications where conservative narrow-band approximations are allowable. Several examples demonstrated and validated the concepts and procedures including the average continuous relative phase, narrow-band multiaxial fatigue solutions, and fatigue reliability. The following two directions are promising and deserve attention in future research: (1) moment of load path and the associated ratio of principal values could be used as an alternative parameter for measuring nonproportionality of loading path, and (2) nonstationary data analysis with the Hilbert transform for wide-band frequency-domain PDMR analysis.

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References

- [1] I. Lotsberg. *Fatigue Design of Marine Structures*, Cambridge University Press. New York, 2016.
- [2] O.F. Hughes and J. K. Paik. *Ship Structural Analysis and Design*, The Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers, Jersey City, New Jersey, 2010.
- [3] R.G. Keane, T. McNatt, J. E. Beach. Reducing total ownership cost: designing robust ship structures. *Naval Engineers Journal*, No.129-4: 93-109, December 2017.
- [4] P. Dong. A structural stress definition and numerical implementation for fatigue analysis of welded joints. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 23: 865–76, 2001.
- [5] P. Dong, J. K. Hong, D. A. Osage and M. Prager. Master S–N curve method for fatigue evaluation of welded components. *Welding Research Council Bulletin*, 2002.
- [6] B. Healy. A case study comparison of surface extrapolation and Battelle structural stress fatigue methodologies. *OMAE-2004*, Vancouver British Columbia, Canada, 2004.
- [7] B. Healy. Hot spot stress analysis of a side shell connection using surface extrapolation and the Battelle structural stress method. *OMAE-FPSO 2004*, August 30-September 2, Hoston, USA, 2004.
- [8] B. Healy. Mesh requirements for surface extrapolation in a side shell connection and a fatigue comparison with the Battelle structural stress method, *OMAE-FPSO 2004*, August 30-September 2, Hoston, USA, 2004.
- [9] P. Dong, Z. Wei, and J. Hong, A path-dependent cycle counting method for variable-amplitude multi-axial loading, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 32: 720-734, 2010.
- [10] Z. Wei and P. Dong. Multiaxial fatigue life assessment of welded structures. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 77: 3011-3021, 2010.
- [11] Z. Wei and P. Dong. A rapid path-length searching procedure for multi-axial fatigue cycle counting. *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, 35: 556-571, 2012.
- [12] Z. Wei and P. Dong. A generalized cycle counting criterion for arbitrary multi-axial fatigue loading conditions. *Journal of Strain Analysis*, 49: 325-341, 2014.
- [13] J. Mei and P. Dong, A new path-dependent fatigue damage model for non-proportional multi-axial loading. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 90: 210-221, 2016.
- [14] J. Mei and P. Dong. Modeling of path-dependent multi-axial fatigue damage in aluminum alloys. *International Journal of Fatigue* 95: 252-263, 2017.
- [15] J. Mei and P. Dong. An equivalent stress parameter for multi-axial fatigue evaluation of welded components including non-proportional loading effects. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 101: 297-311, 2017.
- [16] J. Mei and P. Dong. Analysis of nonproportional multiaxial fatigue test data of various aluminum alloys using a new damage parameter. In Z. Wei, K. Nikbin, P.C. McKeighan, and D.G. Harlow, editors, *Fracture Test Planning, Test Data Acquisitions, and Data Analysis*, pages: 278-298. ASTM STP1598, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2017.
- [17] Z. Wei, P. Dong, J. Mei, X. Pei and S. K. Ravi. A moment of load path-based parameter for modeling multiaxial fatigue damage of welded structures. *International Journal Fatigue*, 171: 107575, 2023.
- [18] Y. L. Lee. *Metal Fatigue Testing and Analysis: Theory and Practice*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2025.
- [19] B. Healy. A comparison of the surface extrapolation and Battelle structural stress methodologies as applied to a spectral fatigue analysis of a representative EPSO structural detail. *OMAE2007-29739*, June 10-15, San Diego, California, USA, 2007.
- [20] B. Healy, B. A comparison of frequency and time domain fatigue damage using the Battelle structural stress methodology. *OMAE 2015-41073*, May 31-June 5, St John's, Newfoundland, Canada, 2015.
- [21] S. K. Ravi and P. Dong. A spectral fatigue method incorporating non-proportional multiaxial loading. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 131:105300, 2020.
- [22] S. K. Ravi, P. Dong and Z. Wei. Data-driven modeling of multiaxial fatigue in frequency domain, *Marine Structures*, 84:103201, 2022.
- [23] X. Pei, S. K. Ravi, P. Dong, X. Li and X. Zhou. A multi-axial vibration fatigue evaluation procedure for welded structures in frequency domain, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, 167: 108516, 2022.
- [24] X. Pei, Y. Cao, T. Gu, M. Xie, P. Dong, Z. Wei, J. Mei, and T. Zhang. Generalizing multiaxial vibration fatigue criteria in the frequency domain: a data-driven approach, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 186: 108390, 2024.
- [25] BS 7608: 2014 Guide to fatigue design and assessment of steel products, London, UK.
- [26] DNV Recommended Practice, DNV-RP-C203, Fatigue Design of Offshore Steel Structures, April 2010, DET NORSKE VERITAS
- [27] Z. Wei, P. Dong and X. Pei. Effective second moment of load path (ESMLP) method for multiaxial fatigue damage and life assessment. *SAE Technical Paper 2023-01-0724*, 2023.

- [28]A. Bolchoun, J. Wiebesiek, H. Kaufmann and C.M. Sonsino. Application of stress-based multiaxial fatigue criteria for laserbeam-welded thin aluminum joints under proportional and non-proportional variable amplitude loadings. *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 73: 9-16, 2014.
- [29]A. Bolchoun, H. Kaufmann, C.M. Sonsino. Numerical measures of the degree of non-proportionality of multiaxial fatigue loadings. *Frattura ed Integrita Strucutrale*, 33: 238-252, 2015.
- [30]C. C. Chu, F.A. Conle and A. Hübner. An integrated uniaxial and multiaxial fatigue life prediction method. *VDI Berichte Nr., 1283 Germany*, 337-348, 1996.
- [31]J. E. Bishop. Characterizing the non-proportional and out-of-phase extent of tensor paths. *Fatigue Frac Engine Materia Struct*, 23: 1019-1032, 2000.
- [32]C. Gaier, H. Dannbauer. Fatigue analysis of multiaxially loaded components with the FE-postprocessor FEMFAT-MAX, *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Biaxial/Multiaxial Fatigue and Fracture*, 1: 223-240, 2001.
- [33]C. Gaier, A. Lukacs and K. Hofwimmer. Investigations on a statistical measure of the non-proportionality of stresses. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 26: 331-337, 2004.
- [34]C. Riess, M. Obermayr and M. Vormwald. The non-proportionality of local stress paths in engineering applications. *Frattura ed Integrita Strucutrale*, 37: 52-59, 2016.
- [35]M. L. Larsen and J. Baumgartner, H.B. Clausen and V. Arora. Multiaxial fatigue assessment of welded joints using a principal component-based measure for non-proportionality. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 158:106731, 2022.
- [36]P. F. Lamb, M. Stöckl. On the use of continuous relative phase: review of current approaches and outline for a new standard. *Clinical Biomechanics*, 29: 484-493, 2014.
- [37]G. D'Elia and E. Mucchi. Comparison of single-input single output and multi-input, multi-output control strategies for performing sequential single-axis random vibration control test. *Journal of Vibration and Control*, 26:1988-2000, 2000.
- [38]S. O. Rice. Mathematical analysis of random noise. *Selected Papers on Noise and Stochastic Processes*, (N.Wax; Ed.) Dover, New York, 1954.
- [39]J. S. Bendat. Probability functions for random response: prediction of peaks, fatigue damage, and catastrophic failures, *National Aeronautics and Space Administration*, NAS-5-4590,
- [40]J. S. Bendat and A.G. Piersol. *Random Data: Analysis and Measurement Procedures*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey, 2010.
- [41]T. Dirlik and D. Benasciutti. Dirlik and Tovo-Benasciutti spectral methods in vibration: a review with historical perspective. *Metals*, 11: 1333, 2021.
- [42]J. W. Miles. On structural fatigue under random loading. *Journal of the Aeronautical Sciences*, 753-762, 1954.
- [43]A. K. Williams and J.E. Rinne. Fatigue analysis of steel offshore structures, *Proc ICE*, Part 1, November 1976.
- [44]M. G. Hallam. Fatigue analysis of off-shore oil platforms, *SEECO'78 Conference, Application of Computes in Fatigue*, April 1978.
- [45]T. M. M. Pillai and A.M. Prasad. Fatigue reliability analysis in time domain for inspection strategy of fixed offshore structures, *Ocean Engineering*, 27: 167-186, 2000.
- [46]M. Gobbi and G. Mastinu. Expected fatigue damage of road vehicles due to road excitation. *Vehicle Systems Dynamics*, 29: 778-788, 1998.
- [47]S. K. Ravi, Z. Wei, P. Dong, P., X. Pei. Modeling of non-proportional multiaxial fatigue under synchronous and asynchronous sinusoidal loading conditions. *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2022, 163: 107000, 2022.
- [48]S. Chandrasekaran. *Offshore Structural Engineering: Reliability and Risk Assessment*. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2016.
- [49]Y. Dong, Y. Garbatov, C.G. Soares. Review on uncertainties in fatigue loads and fatigue life of ships and offshore structures. *Ocean Engineering*, 264: 112514, 2022.